

AT3 White Paper-Part C
Recommendations to Decision-Makers
National Waste Policy 2018

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Introduction

This part C of the white paper presents two evidence-based policy recommendations aimed at enhancing the environmental effectiveness of circular economy (CE) initiatives in Australia’s construction and demolition (C&D) sector. Anchored in the findings of White Paper Part B, which identified limitations in data standardisation and lack of upstream policy support, these recommendations directly address systemic gaps within the National Waste Policy 2018 (NWP 2018). Their purpose is to guide actionable and resource-sensitive reform aligned with national sustainability objectives. The first recommendation proposes mandating nationally standardised environmental performance metrics for CE interventions, while the second recommends incentivising upstream CE strategies through conditional redistribution of landfill levy revenues.

To assess risks and assumptions, this paper employs a Program Logic Model—a structured tool widely used in Australian policy contexts (Centre for Epidemiology and Evidence, 2023)—to trace causal links from inputs to long-term outcomes and to identify where logic gaps may hinder effectiveness (Funnell & Rogers, 2011). In addition, a scenario planning matrix is used to explore how regulatory enforcement and industry uptake may shape CE trajectories. This foresight tool is justified by its proven value in navigating policy uncertainty and stress-testing interventions (Wilkinson & Kupers, 2013). Together, these tools enhance the recommendations’ robustness and relevance under varying future conditions.

Evidence-based Recommendations

Informed by the key limitations identified in the Part B this section presents two targeted, evidence-based policy recommendations. Each proposal is designed to enhance the environmental effectiveness of CE practices in Australia’s C&D sector, in alignment with the objectives of the NWP 2018 and broader commitments under the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Drawing on high-quality empirical evidence and structured using a claim–evidence–reasoning framework, the recommendations are actionable, context-sensitive, and adaptable across varying levels of resource availability. Detailed SMART criteria are presented in Appendix 1 (Bjerke & Renger, 2017) to support implementation planning and performance evaluation under both low- and high-funding scenarios.

Recommendation 1

Claim

The first recommendation is to mandate a set of nationally standardised environmental performance metrics for CE interventions in the C&D sector. These metrics should include indicators such as lifecycle greenhouse gas (GHG) reductions, material recovery rates, and waste-to-landfill ratios.

Evidence

As identified in the rapid review, one of the most significant barriers to evaluating CE effectiveness is the inconsistent or absent use of performance metrics (Dejkovski, 2016; Shooshtarian et al., 2022). Studies such as Ho and Iyer-Raniga (2021) and Iyer-Raniga et al. (2023) reinforce that, although CE practices are endorsed in policy, there is little empirical quantification of outcomes. This lack of data transparency makes it difficult to benchmark interventions or guide resource allocation effectively (Shooshtarian et al., 2022; Wu et al., 2022).

Reasoning

Mandating performance metrics would fill a systemic gap in CE governance, enabling evidence-based planning and fostering accountability across jurisdictions (Zhao et al., 2021; Pilipenets et al., 2024). It directly aligns with NWP 2018's Principle 5 (improve information systems) and Strategy 13 (data and reporting), which call for stronger national data frameworks to support decision-making. A phased approach could be tailored to suit various funding capacities—embedding metrics into existing procurement tools under a low-funding scenario and developing a centralised digital reporting platform under a high-funding model. This recommendation will enable measurable progress toward CE goals by translating policy ambition into tangible outcomes.

Recommendation 2

Claim

The second recommendation is to incentivise upstream CE strategies—such as modular design, design for disassembly, and material passports—by redistributing a portion of landfill

levy revenue as conditional funding for projects demonstrating verified environmental performance improvements.

Evidence

Findings from the rapid review highlight that most CE interventions remain concentrated at the end-of-pipe (recycling and recovery), while upstream strategies receive limited policy or economic support (Iyer-Raniga et al., 2023; Shooshtarian et al., 2021). Shooshtarian et al. (2022) and Zhao et al. (2022) stress that upstream measures are critical to waste prevention but remain underused. Furthermore, Khalfan et al. (2020) report that over 90% of industry stakeholders support landfill levies as a CE policy instrument, especially when linked to reinvestment mechanisms.

Reasoning

Redirecting landfill levy revenue toward upstream interventions creates an economic signal for circular design while maintaining cost-neutrality in public budgeting. It also aligns with NWP 2018's Principle 1 (avoid waste) and Strategy 2 (design for reuse and repair), which emphasise early-stage intervention. This approach supports systemic change by moving beyond recycling as the default CE strategy. In low-funding contexts, modest, fixed grants could be offered for pilot projects. In high-funding scenarios, a performance-based tiered system could reward the most impactful innovations. This balances policy ambition with implementation realism and equity.

Together, these recommendations aim to drive measurable, upstream-focused CE reform by addressing gaps in data, governance, and economic incentives. Grounded in empirical findings from Part B and aligned with NWP 2018, they are designed for high feasibility and policy relevance.

Risk Assessment

A critical risk associated with the National Waste Policy's CE initiatives' environmental effectiveness in the C&D sector is the causal disjunction between short-term interventions—such as sorting infrastructure and design requirements—and the long-term outcomes they are presumed to deliver. This includes overestimating the effectiveness of immediate outputs (e.g., improved waste sorting) in achieving transformative impacts such as significant waste

reduction, material circularity, and lifecycle carbon savings. Ignoring this risk can result in misallocated funding, stalled momentum, and policy disillusionment among key stakeholders.

To analyse this risk, a Program Logic Model was selected as the fit-for-purpose assessment tool. Program logic offers a structured approach to map causal linkages between policy inputs, activities, outputs, and intended short- and long-term outcomes (Funnel & Rogers, 2011; McLaughlin & Jordan, 2015). It is particularly effective for identifying assumptions embedded in transition pathways, making it ideal for unpacking the logic behind complex sustainability interventions (Funnel & Rogers, 2011; McLaughlin & Jordan, 2015). The tool is widely endorsed by Australian policy bodies such as Centre for Epidemiology and Evidence (2023) for its diagnostic value in planning and evaluation contexts.

Application of this tool (Appendix 2) revealed that both recommendations rely heavily on the assumption that regulatory or financial interventions at the input/output level will trigger behavioural and systemic change. However, without parallel investments in education, cross-jurisdictional policy alignment, and adaptive monitoring, long-term change may not materialise. This was especially evident for Recommendation 2, where infrastructure without upstream design standards or market pull mechanisms risks poor utilisation.

These findings suggest the need to revise both recommendations by embedding monitoring systems to test assumptions and ensuring feedback loops to adjust interventions over time. Integrating program logic insights improves the recommendations' realism, enhances stakeholder confidence, and strengthens alignment with circular economy goals.

Exploring Possible Futures

Scenario planning is a strategic foresight method used to explore how complex sustainability challenges might evolve under uncertainty (Wilkinson & Kupers, 2013). It supports adaptive policymaking by identifying key predetermined elements, drivers, and critical uncertainties (Wilkinson & Kupers, 2013). Given the fragmented adoption of CE in Australia's C&D sector and unpredictable regulatory enforcement, this tool is well suited to stress-test the feasibility of proposed interventions (Amer et al., 2013). The 2x2 matrix approach is applied in this context due to its simplicity and widespread use in policy foresight exercises (Futures Platform, 2023).

Two predetermined elements shape the baseline: (1) Australia's ongoing national commitment to reduce landfill reliance via the National Waste Policy 2018 and Action Plan

2019 (Commonwealth of Australia, 2021); and (2) projected growth in C&D waste due to intensified construction and urbanisation (Lim et al. 2024).

Two key drivers shaping change are:

(1) growing industry interest in upstream CE strategies such as design-for-disassembly and modular construction, driven by the potential for lifecycle cost savings and emissions reductions (Pomponi & Moncaster, 2017).; and

(2) the emergence of digital tracking technologies enabling improved monitoring of material flows and performance metrics, which could support circular supply chains and standardised reporting (Reike et al., 2018).

The scenario matrix pivots on two uncertainties: (1) strength of regulatory enforcement (strong vs weak), and (2) industry uptake of CE principles (high vs low). These define four future scenarios (Appendix 3):

- **Circular Renaissance:** Strong enforcement + high uptake—policy and industry mutually reinforce CE outcomes.
- **Mandated Makeover:** Strong enforcement + low uptake—compliance is forced, but innovation lags.
- **Voluntary Vanguard:** Weak enforcement + high uptake—market-driven leadership by frontrunners.
- **Waste Spiral:** Weak enforcement + low uptake—status quo persists with worsening impacts.

In *Circular Renaissance* and *Voluntary Vanguard*, both recommendations show high potential. However, in *Mandated Makeover* and especially *Waste Spiral*, Recommendation 2 becomes less viable due to low industry initiative, making financial incentives insufficient to trigger upstream innovation. In contrast, Recommendation 1—anchored in enforceable metrics—demonstrates greater policy resilience, as it remains implementable even under weak voluntary participation. This supports the rapid review’s emphasis on standardisation gaps and accountability weaknesses in CE performance reporting.

Conclusion

This white paper has traced systemic challenges and policy gaps across the evidence base (Part A), environmental outcomes (Part B), and practical reform strategies (Part C) surrounding the National Waste Policy 2018. It finds that while CE initiatives in Australia's C&D sector offer strong environmental potential, their impact remains constrained by weak data systems, downstream bias, and limited upstream policy design. The key takeaway is clear: without enforceable performance metrics and financial incentives for circular design, CE ambitions risk stagnation. Targeted, evidence-informed reforms—grounded in risk analysis and future scenarios—are essential to deliver measurable, equitable, and scalable sustainability outcomes.

Appendix 1: SMART Tables for Recommendations (adapted from Bjerke & Renger, 2017)

SMART Table: Recommendation 1- Mandate Standardised Environmental Performance Metrics for CE Interventions.

SMART Criteria	High-Funding Scenario	Low-Funding Scenario
Specific	Implementing: DCCEEW & state EPAs; Monitoring: Infrastructure Sustainability Council; Impacted: builders, certifiers, waste processors. Scope: All CE-reporting projects under public procurement. Goal: Establish national consistency in CE environmental reporting.	Implementing: State EPAs; Monitoring: Local councils via procurement audits. Scope: Public infrastructure projects. Goal: Integrate CE indicators into existing procurement frameworks.
Measurable	Impact measured by increased reporting compliance across states and quality of data captured. Target: 100% of public CE projects adopt standard metrics by 2027. KPIs: % of projects reporting GHG reduction, landfill diversion, and resource recovery.	Success measured by integration of minimum viable indicators into current reporting tools. Target: 60% of new public projects use standard metrics by 2026. KPIs: Reporting inclusion in tenders; % of reports with GHG data.
Achievable	Feasible through investment in a national digital CE reporting platform and staff training. Agencies already engaged in environmental monitoring have the capacity to scale.	Leverages existing tools like IS Rating Scheme and council reporting; minimal new resourcing required. Local governments can adapt with guidance.
Relevant	Fully aligned with NWP 2018 Principles 5 and 13. Supports national coordination, data transparency, and enables evidence-based decisions. Addresses industry need for clear performance benchmarks.	Still aligns with NWP 2018 and enables incremental data improvements. Practical for constrained environments.

Time Bound	Pilot program initiated by late 2025; full mandatory compliance by 2027. Timeline aligns with NWP 2018 goals and allows staged rollout.	Adoption begins 2025; majority integration by mid-2026. More conservative due to resource limits.
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SMART Table: Recommendation 2- Incentivise Upstream CE Strategies via Conditional Landfill Levy Redistribution.

SMART Criteria	High-Funding Scenario	Low-Funding Scenario
Specific	Implementing: State Treasury & DEECA; Monitoring: CE auditors and third-party verifiers. Impacted: design firms, mid/large construction companies. Scope: New developments applying upstream CE. Goal: Shift economic incentives toward waste prevention.	Implementing: EPA Victoria; Monitoring: Grant committees. Impacted: small contractors and pilot innovators. Scope: Select pilot projects with upstream CE components. Goal: Provide entry-level support for CE design.
Measurable	Impact measured by reduction in material throughput and increased adoption of upstream tools (e.g., BIM-based passports). Target: 30% reduction in material inputs across funded projects by 2028. KPIs: % of funded projects using DfD, LCA validation.	Success measured by pilot demonstration of avoided waste or resource savings. Target: 10 active pilot projects by 2026. KPIs: Documentation of DfD intent, LCA pre-design reports.
Achievable	Feasible through landfill levy reinvestment; agencies already manage grants. New criteria-based tiers introduced via legislation.	Uses a capped fixed grant model. No need for large system overhauls. Technical consultants can assist recipients.
Relevant	Directly addresses NWP 2018 Principles 1 and 2. Responds to industry demand for economic drivers of design innovation. Builds resilience into CE systems.	Aligns with NWP 2018’s vision for innovation and CE expansion. Enables learning-based governance without high overhead.
Time Bound	Legislation drafted by 2025, rollout begins 2026, results tracked through 2028. Supports alignment with other state waste reforms.	Application rounds in 2025; implementation from 2026. Focus on showcasing feasibility over breadth.

Appendix 2: Risk Assessment Figure

Figure A2 presents a Program Logic Model that maps the causal pathway of the proposed policy interventions aimed at improving the environmental effectiveness of CE initiatives in Australia’s C&D sector. The model illustrates how key inputs, activities, and outputs are expected to lead to short-, medium-, and long-term outcomes aligned with the goals of the National Waste Policy 2018. It also highlights the strategic aim of driving systemic uptake of upstream CE practices such as design-for-disassembly and circular design principles.

Figure A2: Program Logic Model illustrating the causal pathway for enhancing the environmental effectiveness of CE interventions in the C&D sector under the National Waste Policy 2018. Adapted from Centre for Epidemiology and Evidence (2023).

Appendix 3: 2x2 Scenario Planning matrix

This matrix presents four plausible futures based on two key uncertainties: regulatory enforcement and industry uptake of circular economy (CE) strategies. These scenarios—Circular Renaissance, Voluntary Vanguard, Mandated Makeover, and Waste Spiral—reflect different combinations of these variables and illustrate how CE outcomes may evolve under the National Waste Policy 2018. The tool supports evaluation of how the proposed recommendations—standardised metrics and conditional levy incentives—may perform across varied future conditions.

Figure A3: Scenario Planning Matrix: Circular Economy Futures in Australia’s C&D Sector (adapted from Futures Platform, 2023).

Appendix 4: Glossary of Terms

Term	Definition
CE (Circular Economy)	An economic model focused on reducing waste and promoting the continual use of resources through strategies like reuse, recycling, and design for longevity.
C&D Waste	Construction and demolition waste, including materials like concrete, wood, metals, and bricks generated during building and infrastructure development or demolition.
NWP 2018 (National Waste Policy 2018)	Australia’s national policy framework aiming to reduce waste, increase recycling, and promote circular economy practices across all sectors.
Upstream CE Strategies	Circular economy interventions implemented early in the product lifecycle, such as modular design, design for disassembly, and material passports, aimed at preventing waste generation.
End-of-Pipe Interventions	Waste management solutions applied after waste has been generated, such as recycling or landfill diversion. These are contrasted with upstream strategies.
GHG (Greenhouse Gases)	Gases that trap heat in the atmosphere, contributing to climate change. CE strategies often aim to reduce lifecycle GHG emissions from construction.
Program Logic Model	A planning and evaluation tool that maps the causal flow of policy interventions from inputs through to long-term outcomes, helping identify assumptions and risks.
Inputs–Activities–Outputs–Outcomes	The causal chain in a program logic model: Inputs (resources) → Activities (actions taken) → Outputs (direct results) → Outcomes (short-, medium-, long-term impacts).
Assumptions	Unverified beliefs or expectations embedded in policy design, such as the belief that incentives will lead to sustained behavioural change in industry.
SMART Criteria	A framework for actionable recommendations: Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound. Used in Appendices to structure implementation detail.
Lifecycle Assessment (LCA)	A technique to assess environmental impacts associated with all stages of a product's life—from raw material extraction to disposal.
Material Passport	A digital record providing detailed information about the materials used in a building to facilitate reuse, recycling, or safer disposal.

Term	Definition
Design for Disassembly (DfD)	A design approach enabling buildings and components to be taken apart and reused, supporting circular construction.
Landfill Levy	A charge imposed on waste disposed of in landfill, aimed at reducing waste and encouraging recycling or reuse.
Conditional Funding	Financial support tied to the achievement of specific performance criteria (e.g., demonstrating CE practices in project design).
Scenario Planning	A foresight method used to explore how different future contexts may affect policy outcomes. It involves imagining alternative futures based on uncertainties.
2x2 Matrix	A common scenario planning tool using two critical uncertainties to generate four possible future scenarios.
Circular Renaissance	A scenario with strong regulatory enforcement and high industry uptake of CE strategies, leading to optimal outcomes.
Mandated Makeover	A scenario with strong enforcement but low industry uptake; policy drives change, but innovation lags.
Voluntary Vanguard	A scenario where industry leads CE adoption voluntarily in the absence of strong regulation.
Waste Spiral	A pessimistic scenario marked by weak enforcement and low industry uptake, resulting in poor environmental performance.
DCCEEW	Department of Climate Change, Energy, the Environment and Water — lead agency for implementing federal CE policies.
EPA	Environment Protection Authority — state-level agencies responsible for environmental regulation and enforcement.
IS Rating Scheme	Infrastructure Sustainability Rating Scheme, a tool for benchmarking environmental performance in infrastructure projects.
ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance)	A set of non-financial performance indicators used to evaluate an organization's commitment to sustainability, ethical impact, and sound governance practices. Increasingly used in policy and investment decisions.

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